

Logistics Insider

THE RISE AND RISE OF THE HYPERLOCAL DELIVERY MODEL

Sturdy Yet Not Prevailing – The Pharmaceutical Supply Chain: An Engrossed Review

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The pharmaceuticals industry – since the beginning with its major investments in research, reliance on complex chemistry, and sophisticated understanding of human biology – has long been a technologically advanced sector. But with the emergence of new technologies, ever-increasing innovations, edge-to-edge competitions and exploding stakeholders and consumers' demands, are now pushing operations (especially supply and distribution) to the top of pharma's agenda. From continuous manufacturing to digitisation, from biopharmaceuticals (including vaccines) to novel gene therapies and even 3-D printing, there will be major changes in pharma production and supply chains. But there is a dire need of absolute clarity whether the industry is enforcing the right actions in the right direction.

Supply chain management describes the management of all activities in any of the companies involved in a supply chain to provide the highest possible level of customer service at optimum total supply chain cost and investment. Over the last 30 years, supply chain has undergone a tremendous change. From purely operational logistics function that reported

to sales or manufacturing and focused on ensuring supply of production lines and delivery to customers has now become an independent supply-chain management function that in some companies is already being led by a CSO (chief supply-chain officer). The whole world is already at Supply Chain 4.0 and heading towards 5.0 due to humongous disruption by COVID-19 pandemic.

Globally, we have observed the use of Internet of Things (IoT), advanced robotics, analytics, and big data – to jump-start performance, and customer satisfaction in supply chain management around many industrial sectors whether it may be automotive, or food, or electronics, etc. Industries around the world are adopting the changing trend with an equally fast pace. Every industry has its unique characteristics, but those working in pharma would always say that the effective adoption of contemporary supply chain management is difficult due to the regulatory environment that they work in.

R&D is the major focused area of the pharma world since the early ages and that strong product focus of R&D implies a hard impact on the supply chain. In other sectors, R&D is increasingly aimed at improving processes,

as well as developing new products, and both these factors have contributed to the pharma industry arriving late to the game in terms of supply chain process innovation. Secondly, the sluggish decampment of regulatory compliance is another factor which holds down the growth of supply chain processes in the pharma sector.

Any supply chain improvement uses six main drivers to leverage the innovations, i.e., Strategy, Planning, Physical flow, Performance management, Order management, and Collaboration. All along with utmost requirement to recognise the complexity and value of securing the entire value chain for medicines, from production to distribution to patients as well as the drivers that hinder supply security. A predictable and sustainable access to quality medicines fundamentalised the concept of universal health coverage and UN's Sustainable Development Goals.

There are four vitals or absolutes of supply chain management as per Ed Sweeney: the objectives, philosophy, flow and customer/supplier relationships. Objective defines an absolute clarity on the objectives of the supply chain. That can be achieved by enabling high levels of customer service in targeted markets/segments while also optimising total supply chain investment and cost. The whole concept of value and how the supply chain as a collective entity, or as a network of companies, creates that value, works on this basic principle. A High level of integration between companies upstream and downstream in supply chains marks the second absolute i.e., Philosophy. This can be rectified by replacing the fragmented approaches with those that are characterised more by integration. Strengthening linkages between functions can also help to fulfil this target. Logistics has taken a huge step forward through better connectivity, advanced analytics, additive manufacturing, and advanced automation, upending traditional warehousing and inventory-management strategies. The key flow is the flow of information - it is impossible

to imagine any 21st century supply chain being able to operate without a sophisticated and complex IT backbone? Apparently, by working on relationships and creating an ecosystem with high level of mutual trust and benefits, openness and shared goals and objectives, the perfections and advancements can be manifested.

Now, after discussing the supply chain basics, question arises that where is the gap that need to be filled? The simplest yet powerful and justified answer to this question is, "Pharma Industry – just not an early adopter". Perhaps, pharma companies face different competitive pressures to those in the consumer electronics or the automotive industry may be the reason for this. But in the last decade, the level of supply chain professionalism that is quite visible in the pharma sector has increased beyond recognition.

Amid coronavirus crisis, on one hand the evident modulation and amplified efforts of the industry to meet the challenging demands, boosted the whole infrastructure of the pharma supply chain. On the other hand, it added complications too like the temperature-controlled logistics to distribute the approved COVID-19 vaccines. The need of the hour is to design and eliminate out the complexities with such a supply chain that can take care not only the distribution of the vaccine to patients, but the pre-manufacturing, manufacturing and everything in between.

At last, diversification of the supply chain will remain important and systemic and sustainable policy reforms will underpin such ambition. The pharma supply chains are need to be re-imagined in a very logical and systematic way. Also, it is equally important to prepare it for large scale responses with sufficient value proposition. Along with the improvement and investment in R&D, the pharma sector has to charge its supply chain and roll-out a trending and robust value chain model which maximises the productivity, profit, healthcare, customer satisfaction and more oriented towards the synergistic collaborations.